

The Power of Digitalization in Health Crisis

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the implementation of the mobile application to aid in the outbreak management. In this paper, the 2020 outbreak of Covid-19 is used, with the Netherlands as a geographical point of interest. Therefore, will be focused on the effects the application has on the Dutch systems and processes, including the Gemeenschappelijke Gezondheidsdienst (GGD).

This paper contains an IT Governance assessment from a pre- and post-Covid analysis of the testing processes. Moreover, risk assessments of the 'CoronaMelder' are performed to see why its predecessors failed. On a final note, while this paper is using Covid-19 outbreak as a case, the goal is to have impact for future pandemics, so that the future is better prepared for anything that happens. An application might seem easy to create and implement but in reality hosts a lot of issues and risks before it can be released for public use.

Keywords

Corona-app, GGD, risk assessment, Covid-19, GDPR

INTRODUCTION

Since the start of the Covid-19 pandemic many governments have tried different approaches to containing the virus and tracing the spread pattern. The Dutch government combined with the Gemeenschappelijke Gezondheidsdienst (GGD) chose the approach of source investigation and contact tracing. In short this means that once a person is positively tested on the Covid-19 virus, the patient will receive a call from the GGD asking him or her about their contacts since they have been contagious. This is a relatively work intensive process which requires more employees since the increase in active

cases. Furthermore, there have been cases where positively tested patients have refused to work together with the GGD in the contact tracing.

Throughout the world, various governments have tried different approaches to digitalizing the contact tracing process. The question that this paper will focus on is the effectiveness of digitizing an existing process during a crisis.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Research will be performed on the effectiveness of digital transformation during a health crisis. The process that will be taken as an example for the research is changing the contact tracing, which is currently being performed manually by people in call centers, to a process which is mainly automated by an app. Several other governments worldwide have adopted this method of contact tracing. The goal of the paper is to research the effectiveness of adopting a new process. One could argue that a new process could replace the old process, whilst others could argue that a new process will only work side by side with the original until the new process is fully developed and has few to no flaws. Since this situation is new, due to the fast emerging coronavirus, not much research has been done. By comparing non-crisis digital transformations to the plans of the Dutch government and other governments around the world, this paper will answer the research question.

RESEARCH QUESTION

With this information in mind, the main research question of this paper will be:

To what extent does the CoronaApp have an effect on the workload of GGD?

METHODS

In this research we mainly used desk research as a primary research method. The corona pandemic is fairly recent, however it has such a big impact on our lives, that plenty of research is available. We used a lot of external archival research, meaning that we used papers available online. Furthermore, the information about the covid-19 processes of GGD is available online. The theory is used from several papers that helped us with our research. We did use some primary research, such as interviewing multiple experts in the field. These experts are all lecturers at the University of Tilburg.

ANALYSIS IT GOVERNANCE

The Covid-19 virus has a great impact on the health sector. Specifically, on the workload of the Gemeenschappelijke Gezondheidsdienst (GGD). In the before situation, we will investigate the current situation of contact tracing without an application and how it can be improved during the pandemic. Since the pandemic is still ongoing and is not going away anytime soon, we have to improve the current process to relieve the workload for the GGD. We are using a case study in the Netherlands, but is generalizable globally, this case study can also be used for future pandemics.

In this case study we analyse two major organizations that are closely related, which are the GGD, which is a government institution, and the Dutch government. The coronavirus has spread globally more and more and therefore data about contact tracing needs to be available. Consequently, the process of contact tracing by the GGD is very difficult and costs a lot of time. The reason why contact tracing is so important is because the virus should not spread any further, the (possibly) infected people should be quarantined as soon as possible. Therefore a smooth process is required so that the GGD can actually inform everyone that got into contact with an infected person.

Table 1: IT governance matrix Weil & Ross

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Architecture	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy		Government						Government		Government
IT Monarchy				CIO IT-leaders		CIO IT-leaders				
Federal		Biz leaders		VWZ				VWZ		
Federal		RIVM GGD				RIVM GGD		RIVM		SLA GGD
IT Duopoly		IT leaders		Ministres						
Anarchy										

See appendix A for a larger version.

Governance mechanisms:

RIVM: Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid & Milieu
 VWS: Ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn & Sport
 Government: Dutch government
 CIO: CIO staff
 IT leaders: IT leadership groups
 Biz leaders: departments of health, security
 SLA: Service Level Agreement

The Covid-19 pandemic is very unstable until a vaccine is available, which means that the GGD will undergo many changes. The GGD provides the coronatests and includes the numbers of the amount of positive and negative tested people in the country. There are multiple GGD branches spread nationally, so that everyone is eligible for testing. Each day, the GGD takes notice of how many people were tested and how many of those were tested positively for Corona. This is a great input resource for the decision makers. The government is taking actions based on the number of positive cases. Due to the increasing number of covid-19 cases, measures will be made, such as a lockdown. Therefore, these numbers from GGD are necessary for decisions.

Furthermore, the government will take all the decisions and they have organizations that advise them, such as the RIVM. The RIVM is a government institution that provides consultation to the government on what actions should be done. The (Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports (VWZ) is the minister of health department in The Netherlands and is responsible for the actions to be made. In the end, the government is accountable for nearly all of these decisions.

Before the covid-19 pandemic, the department of health was not very active in decision making. Since the pandemic the VWZ has seen a great impact, the workload has increased and a great responsibility lays in their hands. The impact from the pandemic has resulted in great responsibility of the department of health. This is due to a pandemic that is specifically harming the general public's health.

RIVM mainly gives advice on what the business application should contain. The overall decision about the corona-app is the government and VWZ. They decide how the application should function and what information should be exchanged. The government is therefore reliant on the RIVM for input, since they provide the consultation. The application should meet the requirements of the privacy aspects and the technical aspects that the government will decide.

For IT investment, the government is in full charge. The government decides how much should and can be spent on the development of the application. The application should be available to a vast majority of the population in the Netherlands, besides from children who most likely don't have access to a mobile phone. The Dutch government is therefore also in charge of what the IT budget should be spent on. The GGD gives input on how many people are infected with the COVID-19 virus. This helps decide where the Government should spend its budget on. Furthermore, the SLA will also provide input on how much the application is being used. It monitors the activity of people and provides more information to the government.

BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

The present chapter aims to explore the shift in the testing and outbreak-research processes with the aid of a COVID-19 app in finding and alerting infected people. This is done through a set of Business Process models, one for both before and after the implementation of a COVID-19 app, along with short descriptions.

General limitations:

- The diagrams are simplified for illustration purposes. For example, the diagram does not take into account patients with severe symptoms, needing to be hospitalized. Taking such patients into consideration requires another layer to the diagram, which would not add benefit to the illustration of the application's use.
- While official RIVM and GGD documents, as well as COVID-19 application concepts were consulted for the creation of these diagrams, they are largely based on assumptions. For this reason, short descriptions of the processes are included below.

Pre-Covid Testing Process:

For a graphical representation of the pre-covid testing process, please refer to **appendix B**. Presently, prior to the launch of a COVID-19 app, all testing and outbreak research is done through the GGD. Someone who feels sick is notated as a patient, which is where the process starts.

This person assesses their own symptoms and decides whether they want to get tested or not, depending on their preferences, the severity of the symptoms and their personal traits (e.g. whether they have pre-existing conditions). If they decide to, they

should self-isolate for 7 days, as posed by the GGD and RIVM guidelines (*Informatie Voor Een Positief Geteste COVID-19-Patiënt in de Thuisituatie*, 2020; RIVM, 2020).

In the case they do decide to get tested, as is strongly encouraged and advised, an appointment is made by phone or online. The patient visits a nearby testing facility to perform the test. The result is later sent to them, following which they must either follow self-isolation guidelines, or are cleared as COVID-19 negative. In the case of the former, the GGD will perform research into relatives and contacts of the infected patient. Such affected individuals are contacted and advised to self-isolate and stay alert for symptoms. In the case of identified symptoms, those people become patients themselves and go through the entire process again. Those not showing symptoms are urged to self-isolate for 10 days, following which they are cleared as not infected.

Post-covid Testing Process:

For a graphical representation of the pre-covid testing process, please refer to **appendix C**. The diagram remains unchanged for the most part, only adding a new layer for the application, a way for potentially infected individuals to be contacted, and an option for positively tested patients to notify the application of their infection. The new or affected elements have been highlighted in green.

The application process is based on official documentation for the proposed COVID-19 application, as well as relevant news articles (Verbeek et al., 2020; Verhagen, 2020). Following being installed, the initiating event in the application process, the application constantly monitors for nearby Bluetooth devices, as indicated by a loop in the diagram. All applications have a unique, however anonymized, code. Such codes of nearby devices are saved for a limited time and remain on the application's central server. When a patient notifies the application of their infection, their device's unique code is flagged in the central server. When an application pings the server, which is done every few hours, the central server returns any flagged codes saved on the device, thereby notifying the user of their encounter with an infected individual. Following this notification, the user enters the process of "potentially infected people", as has been described in the pre-covid diagram.

None of the GGD processes are replaced, however, they have been supplemented with the application. This will translate to more people being aware of their potential infection, as well as relieve some of GGD's work, rather than replace it. The

result of this is a minor reduction in the workload of the GGD in the contact-tracing process. On the whole, GGD’s workload in the Covid-19 testing process might even increase, as more people become aware of an encounter with an infected person, and therefore decide to contact officials. Overall, the mobile application is unlikely to have a significant impact on the GGD’s workload in the testing process.

CYBERSECURITY MANAGEMENT

The Covid-19 increased GGD’s workload significantly. Therefore, the government made the decision to make use of technology in support of contact tracing. To lower the workload CoronaMelder has to work properly. Several objectives have to be met. It is critical that the usability of the CoronaMelder is sufficient for all its users, and devices in the 1,5 meter proximity are detected. Further, privacy risks have to be taken into account with the purpose that more citizens will in fact make use of CoronaMelder.

The decision to develop and implement CoronaMelder bears substantial risks, the application to be used should therefore be chosen accordingly. The timeline of this process, regarding CoronaMelder, can be found in table 2.

Table 2

Date	Activity
April 6 th	OMT advises to explore possibilities in support of contact tracing (for example an application).
April 8 th	VWS (Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports) announces market exploration concerning digital methods in support of contact tracing.
18-19 April	Appathon. Seven competitors present their applications.
April 22 nd	Appathon applications don’t meet government requirements. VWS decides to develop an application.
June 8 th	Technical testing Covid-application. Focus point is Bluetooth, specifically distance (1,5m) and contact duration.
End June	Conversations about usability. 100 people were inquired, more filled out an online questionnaire.
End June	Lab-test on usability by University of Twente.
July 8 th	Name application announced: CoronaMelder
July	Accessibility test with vulnerable user groups (blind/bad eyesight, deaf/bad hearing, non-Dutch speakers).
8-13 July	Large field-test, 1500 participants in Twente and 500 in representative focus groups. Participants are testing the application in their home environment, using their own device.
July 16 th	Announcement predetermined introduction CoronaMelder
Mid-end July	Concept DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) by Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens (Dutch Data Protection Authority). Development team executes a penetration test.
August	Optimization work processes based on the conducted field-tests.

From 17th of August Field-testing in GGD-regions (public health service) Twente and Rotterdam-Rijnmond. CoronaMelder is working properly and available in app stores. Only GGD Twente and Rotterdam-Rijnmond support the application, as for now.

September 1st Predetermined national introduction Coronamelder.

Covid-19 increased GGD's workload significantly by giving them many more tasks such as calling around to relatives that could have been in contact with the patients or recording the cases tested and tested positive to give a representation of how well or bad it is going in the Netherlands. Therefore, the decision was made to make use of technology in support of contact tracing. This decision bears a lot of risks, as the application has to be used for official purposes and should therefore be chosen accordingly. The timeline of this process can be found in table 2 along with how it went down and the change of plans. As stated in the timeline, seven competitors failed to deliver a functioning Covid-19 app that met all requirements. The government therefore decided to develop an Covid-19 application themselves. CoronaMelder and Corvid-19 applications in general gained a lot of negative media attention regarding security risks and privacy concerns. The following risks were determined (1) the application does not comply with GDPR (Bradford, et al., 2020), (2) Privacy is not sufficiently guaranteed (Dutch Data Protection Agency) (Beskorovajnov, et al., 2020). Also, (3) Contact tracing is not precise enough (1,5M) (Hernández-Orallo, et al., 2020), (4) a leak of (personal) data (Beskorovajnov, et al., 2020), and (5) data is wrongfully used by third party (DPA, 2020). Further (6) a type I error in application could occur, a (7) type II error in application could follow. Lastly, (8) Phishing attacks (Singh Lallie, et al., 2020), and (9) malicious applications (Singh Lallie, et al., 2020).

A risk assessment regarding these nine risks has been made and can be found in the following table (3), a distinction between a normal and vulnerable user group is made here. The vulnerable user group is defined by a group that consists of people that are old and/or people that have very little to no experience with using apps. These people are the most vulnerable for getting targeted by cybercriminals.

Table 3

Risk	Likelihood x Impact normal user group			Likelihood x Impact vulnerable* user group		
	L	I	Assessment	L	I	Assessment
Application does not comply with GDPR	3	5	15	3	5	15
Privacy is not sufficiently guaranteed	4	4	16	4	4	16
Contact tracing is not precise enough	4	5	20	4	5	20
Leak of (personal) data	3	4	12	3	4	12
Data is wrongfully used by third party	3	4	12	3	4	12
Type I error in application	3	2	6	3	2	6
Type II error in application	1	5	5	4	5	20
Phishing attacks	2	4	8	4	4	16
Malicious applications	2	4	8	4	4	16

*vulnerable group = This group consists of people that are old and/or people that have very little to no experience with using apps. These people are the most vulnerable for getting targeted by cybercriminals.

The table displays many high risks, of which some bear more risk than others. Contact tracing has the highest risk factor, since the application relies on contact tracing to achieve the desired result of reliable information. Secondly, the risk that privacy is not sufficiently guaranteed. This risk is high, because

citizens are not likely to install the application, when the DDPA is unsure about its safety. The risk regarding the GDPR is less high, since it is more likely the GDPR is taken into consideration during the development phase. Finally, a data leak and data being wrongfully used by a third is stated as a general risk to both user groups. Considering, the application is developed rapidly agreements about data use have not been made with third parties, like Google and Apple.

The government should not take big risks in regard to citizens' privacy and health. There should be a balance between risk and reward, in this case the reward is public health. Proportionate measures have to be taken, thus the level of risk will be minimal to cautious. The risk appetite chosen in this risk assessment is ten. Consequently, eight risks need further attention to reduce them, before the application can be introduced and implemented. These risk are as follows:

1. Application does not comply with GDPR
2. Privacy is not sufficiently guaranteed
3. Contact tracing is not precise enough
4. Leak of (personal) data
5. Data is wrongfully used by third party
6. Type II error in application
7. Phishing attacks
8. Malicious applications

Recommendations

Firstly, the recommendations given are based on the information available about the Dutch government's app "CoronaMelder". From the risk assessment, one could conclude that risks of these applications are currently being estimated as high.

1. Application does not comply with GDPR

To make sure the application complies with the GDPR, specialized lawyers should verify if this is the case. Recommended adjustments by the lawyers should be implemented by the developers to ensure no problems arise with the GDPR. What this will create is a more solid base that the government can work with and comply with the European legislation. The government currently has a high standard team

of lawyers which should be able to provide the needed documentation and adjustments to create a proper application.

2. Privacy is not sufficiently guaranteed

When it comes to privacy, the DDPA (Dutch Data Protection Agency) should be consulted for this case in relation to the possibility of all privacy issues. Due to the nature of the application that will be launched, which is registering with whom the user has been in contact prior to testing positive, the application will generate a lot of data from every user. If not properly protected, this data could fall in the wrong hands of agencies that will use it for example to advertise or blackmail specific users. The user itself can't see with whom he or she has been in contact due to private key encryption, but if a hacker gathers all data including the names linked to the anonymous keys that are available, it could be disastrous. This could potentially lead to bad practices such as blackmailing or other crimes. To lower this risk, the development team should maximize the application's security and potentially only store the name of the user on the local device and never transfer the name to lower the chance of data leaks and personal information being stolen in the process.

3. Contact tracing is not precise enough

The first risk is that contact tracing is not precise enough due to the hardware limitations. Every user will most likely have a different device with different hardware built in. This hardware is of high importance because it needs to be able to detect the distance of the other users. If hardware is outdated, there is a potential problem with the reliability of the app and the possibility of detecting others around the user. This could potentially result in type 2 errors, due to the application not being able to register the presence of other users within a certain range. Furthermore, the application does not register when and where you were in contact with others. Because of the usage of bluetooth to register the presence of others, a potential flaw could be that one was in contact with a positively tested user whilst driving past them on the road or on the highway during a traffic jam. Another possible flaw could be that two persons are in a different room, both sitting close to a wall and the app registering the close presence of another person. If one of these persons would indicate a positive test result, the other would be notified that they have been in close contact with a positively tested individual. In order to lower the risk, the tracing should be as precise as possible, to ensure that, they should ensure the measurements are

accurate even if there is noise in the measurement, this could be done by for example adding more types of measurements beside the standard one or adding a new measuring dimension. Another recommendation is to add a functionality which shows users the approximate date and time in which they have potentially been in contact with a positively tested individual.

4. Leak of (personal) data

This risk can be decreased by implementing recommendations made by the DDPA. Anonymization of data is a way of reducing the personal data, this way when a data leak happens the data won't be traceable to a specific application user. Furthermore, the contact information should be encrypted to only be viewed by the actual user of which this contact information is or it should be stored in the device locally. This will lower the risk in potential data leaks. Once a data leak occurs, the app loses trust and the functionality of the app will go down due to the lower amount of users actually using the application.

5. Data is wrongfully used by third party

This is a very big problem nowadays. A lot of information is being sold left and right by many companies in order to make a few extra dollars. This risk can be minimized by anonymizing your data so it can't be used maliciously. Furthermore they can keep as much data as possible inside its own circle so third parties have the least amount of data they can use. Guaranteeing the security of data and it not being sold to other companies can also increase the potential for general adoption of users. Some users might be scared that their data will fall in the hands of large companies that sell it to make a profit. Ensuring that this does not happen could potentially increase the willingness of users.

6. Type II error in application

Another risk with a high assessment is the chance for a type 2 error with the vulnerable target group. This group consists of people that are old and/or people that have very little to no experience with using apps. Therefore, these people are the most vulnerable for getting targeted by cybercriminals. The chances of the full group of vulnerable people having a smartphone which can run the app is low. A more likely scenario is that two thirds of the group would have the app installed. Since the vulnerable group has little to no experience dealing with apps, there is a higher chance of the app malfunctioning. If an user

turns off the bluetooth by accident, the app will not function and will not register the presence of others. If one of those people that has been in contact with our vulnerable user was tested positive, the vulnerable user will not be notified due to switched off bluetooth. This will then result in a type 2 error. Another error that could occur is the type 1 error in case the individual accidentally reports to have been tested positive. This could happen in the same way as a pocket dial. We recommend using push notifications in case the bluetooth is switched off by accident. Furthermore, it is recommended to set up the app in a way that it has full access to the bluetooth functionality whilst running.

7. Phishing attack

The biggest vulnerable group, the elderly and computer illiterates, are more likely to get phished by emails or texts from "the corona application" which in reality are people who intend to use the information privately. A single email from "the company" to a message on your phone from representatives, in order to keep the risk as low as possible, the developers of the corona application must actively campaign showing that there is no phone number or email address specifically for the corona app and that everything of the application either goes through the application itself such as creating a help menu or through the official government website such as the RIVM or rijksoverheidsdienst. This change will create a lower risk of such attacks and valuable data being stored more safely. The safety won't only be about inside the application but also to stop your complete phone from being copied through the corona application messages that aren't from the government in other words, a phishing attack.

8. Malicious applications

Malicious applications form a special risk for the vulnerable target group as shown in Table 3 during the risk assessment. Due to the limited knowledge of our target group about technology and applications, there is a higher chance of them falling for malicious applications pretending to be the 'CoronaMelder' or a different version of it. These apps can then get access to more information on the victims phone. Eventually, hackers could gather personal information such as geolocation or caller history about their victim.

To conclude, overall the application has a lot of potential, but also a lot to improve. When looking at the risk assessment, a risk appetite of 10 was taken

into consideration. When looking at our vulnerable target group, we can see that eight out of nine risks were assessed with ten or higher. By implementing the application, the government tries to protect the vulnerable part of the population, which contains many of our vulnerable target group individuals. But what is concluded from the risk assessment is that the potential risk is high if the application is implemented in this way. The most important risk assessed is Type II error in application. This is due to the risk for the vulnerable target group.

CONCLUSION

As seen, contact tracing is far more difficult than it initially seemed, creating an application for the Dutch government and the GGD had to go through strict supervision and no company succeeded. Many failed on the privacy (GDPR) which resulted in the government having to create its own application. From an IT-governance perspective, the change in the departments of the GGD is interesting. As being known as a more relaxed governmental institution, the GGD had to change into a crisis unit where the calls would start to come in and out daily and in big volumes. The GGD had the important task to record positive cases and amount tested and contact close relatives of the positive tested person to ensure the spread is minimized. The corona-application would help in digitalizing the workload for the GGD as now patients can enroll in the application and state they got infected, it will send the link directly to the people the patient has come in contact with.

According to the (Business) Process Models, a Covid-19 application is most likely to reduce the workload of the GGD in the contact-tracing process. When it comes to the overall testing process, it is unlikely that the workload will be reduced. On the contrary, in certain aspects the workload might even increase in the testing process due to the increased number of people with Covid-19 warnings. The impact the application has on the testing process is a fourth layer, complementing the overall process by providing a new avenue for people to realize they have encountered the virus. This new layer concludes with a notification to the user, subsequently progressing into the preexisting “potentially infected person” process. Thereby, it serves purely as an addition, rather than a replacement of an existing process.

When taking a look at cybersecurity a lot of different risk factors arise, the most important that pop out are the GDPR, type I and type II error, contact tracing not accurate enough and hacking

attempts. The distinction is made between the regular user and vulnerable users such as elderly and computer/IT illiterates, this is done as they are more likely to fall for hacking, phishing and misunderstanding the application than the regular user as well as having more destructive results of getting Covid-19. The new corona application must ensure that all risk factors given above will be handled and tackled by for example adding extra steps to ensure security and testing on a proper scale for correct testing. Our recommendation for tackling the issues are focused on keeping everything inside the application, when possible, such as pop up messages as well as having a proper campaign to spread awareness. Another big issue that has to be tackled is privacy as the application will have to provide that it has enough security to follow the GDPR. Anonymity is central to this topic by creating private keys that can only be accessed by the GGD.

If the government can focus on tackling all security issues, the application can have a significant impact on GGD’s workflow. The main benefits lay in outbreak management, control and measurement. The workload is unlikely to be significantly in- or decreased, instead being reallocated to different priorities. Therefore the overall effect will be a shift of responsibilities, maybe a few less callers are needed but those will be replaced by IT specialists as the application will create more questions especially by the vulnerable group. The process will yet again change and the question is if the change will come to the right place or if the Covid-19 application will be another false security to get people’s attention on staying safe during this pandemic.

DISCUSSION

The academic relevance of this paper is quite high. Because a global pandemic like the covid-19 has not occurred in multiple decades. Therefore, we find this research to be relevant for the whole academic industry and for the future. This is due to the fact that if there is another pandemic in the future and the technology that is created today is applicable to the next outbreak too, then this paper can be used as reference from previous experiences and as a note to work on for the future. Furthermore, the managerial relevance is also quite high because the IT industry can assist with implementation of technology during pandemics. As we saw with the current situation in The Netherlands, where multiple organizations were invited to propose a corona-app solution. The same could happen in the future where organizations outside of the government could help develop a solution, such as a website or application. Future

works should focus on seeing the current/past developments after this paper is written as when this paper was written, a new corona application from the government is currently being constructed. Furthermore another pandemic might require another approach by following another group for example or a different approach such as other electronics could be used. This paper is written under the knowledge of students and the growing problems of Covid-19 and thus should be taken both seriously but also critically as things might change over time.

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APPENDIX A: IT GOVERNANCE MATRIX

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Archetype	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy		Government						Government		Government
IT Monarchy				CIO IT-leaders		CIO IT-leaders				
Feudal	Biz leaders		VWZ					VWZ		
Federal	RIVM GGD				RIVM GGD		RIVM		SLA GGD	
IT Duopoly	IT leaders	Ministers								
Anarchy										

APPENDIX B: PRE COVID-19 APP

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APPENDIX C: POST COVID-19 APP

